

私有仓库快照密码学防伪承诺

Cryptographic Proof Commitment for Private Repository Snapshot

最小公开承诺 / Minimal Public Commitment

本文件登记一个私有仓库快照的最小暴露密码学承诺。完整文件清单、文件路径、文件名与仓库内容不在本文件中公开，仅由登记方私下保存，用于未来公开版本发布后的复核。

This document registers a minimal-disclosure cryptographic commitment for a private repository snapshot. The full manifest, repository paths, file names, and repository contents are not disclosed in this document. They are retained privately for later verification after public release.

承诺信息 / Commitment Data

Manifest SHA-256 / 清单 SHA-256

e6c9aa8976aa1e39e7533273807b588c28a1ab762069d382c5e62a4fbbcc3532

Git commit hash / Git 提交 hash

df0c40ceaa4845f11f6e2092a6ec9161d38fd355

Working tree dirty / 工作区是否 dirty

false

Generated at UTC / UTC 生成时间

2026-07-03T17:32:58.7840181+00:00

Generated at local time / 本地生成时间

2026-07-04T01:32:58.7841862+08:00

Snapshot tool version / 快照工具版本

1.2.2

Verification Statement / 验证声明

未来验证时，应检出相同 Git 提交，使用该提交内的 `zenodo_proof_snapshot/new_zenodo_proof_snapshot.ps1` 以相同文件选择规则重新生成 `manifest.csv` 与 `manifest.sha256`。若重新生成的 `manifest.sha256` 与本文件登记值一致，则说明对应文件集合与文件内容匹配该登记快照。

For later verification, the same Git commit should be checked out and the `zenodo_proof_snapshot/new_zenodo_proof_snapshot.ps1` script from that commit should be run with the same file-selection rule to regenerate `manifest.csv` and `manifest.sha256`.

If the regenerated `manifest.sha256` matches the value registered in this document, the corresponding file set and file contents match the registered snapshot.

Disclosure Note / 披露说明

本文件有意不包含 `manifest.csv`、文件路径、文件名、文件数量、仓库名称、操作系统信息或完整 Git 状态，以降低公开登记时的信息暴露。

This document intentionally omits `manifest.csv`, file paths, file names, file count, repository name, operating system details, and full Git status to reduce information exposure during public registration.